

Two Dieri Myths

recorded by Otto Siebert

Adapted from:

Otto Siebert: Sagen und Sitten der Dieri und Nachbarstämme in Zentral-Australien. In: *Globus* 97 (1910), no. 3, pp. 44–50; no. 4, pp. 53–59.
https://www.digi-hub.de/viewer/image/DE-11-001832362/62/LOG_0076/

Translated from German to English

by Eric Paul Bredvik)

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The Origin of Marriage Regulations.¹ A Dieri Myth

Adapted from: p. 46 (No. 4) in the primary source

Narrator: unidentified

Time of recording: prior to 1910

Interlinear translation:

Múra-Múra pínaru Dítjimínkandru wápana wónti-wórida
Mura-Mura alt von Dítjimínka gehend war weit

Mura-Mura old from Dítjimínka going was far

kúpa kúratérila¹³⁾ Jélkapálupáluna já ngátamúra
Kinder zu zeugen, den Jelkapalupaluna und Kinder

children to beget,² the Jélkapálupáluna and children

núnkani, mánkara wórana. Tjáutjau pántjináni
seine, Mädchen einige. Durcheinander werdend

his, girls some. Confusion becoming

pínaru wóra ngánkamálina wónti púnti málila.
alte Männer einige unterredend waren zu teilen einander.

old men some parleying were to separate each other.

Jidni pádi mádu wápamai kaúalka kúratérila.
Du Raupe madu gehe Krähe zu zeugen.

You caterpillar madu go crow to beget.

¹ See Journ. Anthr. Inst., Vol. 34, p. 129.

¹²⁾ Siehe Journ. Anthr. Inst., Vol. 34, p. 129.

² Literally: child lay down for oneself from kurala = to lay.

¹³⁾ Wörtlich: Kind sich hinlegen; für sich hinlegen von kurala = legen.

Jidni	kaúalka	mádu	wápamai	wárukáti	kóratérila.
Du	Krähe	madu	gehe	Emu	zu zeugen.
You	crow	madu	go	emu	to beget.
Jidni	windri	mítani	jínkanáni	wónki	ngámamai,
Du	nur	auf der Erde	deiner	ruhig	wohne,
You	only	on the earth	your	calmly	dwell,
wodéri	Múra-Múra	jínkani	wírarina	wónti.	
wo	Mura-Mura	dein	herumgehend	war.	
where	Mura-Mura	your	going around	was.	

Free translation:

(Ein alter Mura-Mura ging von Dítjimínka fort, um in der Ferne Kinder zu zeugen, den Jélkapálupáluna und andere Kinder, nämlich seine [bekannten] Mädchen¹⁴). [Nachdem diese sich vermehrt hatten] entstand ein Durcheinander, so daß einige alte Männer übereinkamen [die Menschen in Klassen] zu teilen. [Sie sagten]: Du zum Raupe-madu Gehörender gehe hin und zeuge Krähenkinder, du zum Krähen-madu Gehörender gehe hin und zeuge Emukinder. Wohne nur in deiner Gegend, in der einst dein Mura-Mura herumgewandert ist.)

An old Mura-Mura went away from Dítjimínka to beget children far away, the Jélkapálupáluna and other children, namely his [known] girls.³ [After these had increased in number]

³ This refers to the known girls appearing in the Wápia legend (Howitt, l. c. [»Legends of the Dieri and Kindred Tribes of Central Australia.« *The Journal of the Anthropological Institute of Great Britain and Ireland* 34:100-129], p. 119).

¹⁴) Gemeint sind die in der Wápia-Legende (Howitt, l. c., p. 119) vorkommenden bekannten Mädchen.

there was a confusion, so that some old men agreed to separate [the people into classes]. [They said:] You who belong to the caterpillar-madu, go and beget crow children, you who belong to the crow-madu, go and beget emu children. Live only in your area, in which your Mura-Mura once roamed.

Wáritájina (The Fish-Eater)

Adapted from: p. 47 (No. 7) in the primary source

Narrator: unidentified

Time of recording: prior to 1910

Interlinear translation:

Kíllawíllina Pándondru Pírigúndia wápana túrumánja
Kíllawíllina von Pando her nach Pírigúndi gehend Feuerbrand

Kíllawíllina from Pando to Pírigúndi going firebrand

padákana wónti já nájina wónti Pírigúndi - pinnaru
tragend war und sehend war den Pírigúndi alten Mann

carrying was and seeing was the Pírigúndi old man

Wáritájinína páru káti tájináni. Kíllawíllili nína
Wáritájinína Fische roh essend. Kíllawíllina ihn

Wáritájinína fish raw eating. Kíllawíllina him

kárkana wónti já nína kúrokúrobána wónti, wáta
rufend war und ihn ermahnend war, nicht

calling was and him exhorting was, not

mórla káti, aái pándra tájinánto. Nína pádana
mehr roh, sondern gekocht essen sollte. Ihn fassend

anymore raw, but cooked eat should. Him grabbing

núllu	táli	nína	kulírkana	wónti	já	páru	pándra
er	Zunge	ihn	reinigend	war	und	Fisch	gekocht
he	tongue	him	cleaning	was	and	fish	cooked
jínkina	wónti.	Nakáldra	núlu	nína	kúrokúrobána		
gebend	war.	Nochmals	er	ihn	ermahnend		
giving	was.	Again	he	him	exhorting		
wónti,	milingeru	pándralu	tájinánto.	Jéndrangútandru			
war,	immer	gekocht nur	essen sollte.	Seitdem			
was,	always	cooked only	eat should.	Since then			
bákana	Wáritájili	páru	pándralu	tájina	wónti.		
auch	Wáritájina	Fisch	gekocht nur	essend	war.		
also	Wáritájinína	fish	cooked only	eating	was.		

Free translation:

[The primary source does not provide a ›free translation‹ for this narrative. Ours is based on the interlinear version.]

Kíllawíllina, going from Pando to Pírigúndi and carrying a fire-brand, saw the old Pírigúndi man Wáritájinína eating raw fish. Kíllawíllina called out to him and exhorted him to not eat raw [food] anymore, but cooked. Grabbing him, he cleaned his tongue and gave him cooked fish. Again he exhorted him to always only eat cooked [food]. Since then Wáritájinína has also only eaten cooked fish.